

Examining the impact and limitations of Open Science training: a case study of the "Open Seeds" programme

Authors: Paz Bernaldo, Gustavo Pereyra Irujo, Yo Yehudi, Anelda Van der Walt, Irene Ramos, Bethan Iley, Paz Miguez, Esther Plomp, Patricia Herterich, Malvika Sharan

Keywords: Open Science, Open Science training, mentoring, programme impact.

Authors for correspondence: Paz Bernaldo, email: pazbernaldo@gmail.com; Yo Yehudi, email: yo@we-are-ols.org.

Electronic supplementary material is available online at: Bernaldo, P., & OLS. (2025). Supporting materials for "Examining the impact and limitations of Open Science training: a case study of the "Open Seeds" programme" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024935>

1. Introduction	2
2. Methods	4
2.1. Approach to the research	4
2.2. Participants	5
2.3. Data generation	6
2.4. Data analysis	6
2.5 Ethics	8
3. Results	8
3.1. First overarching theme: The pursuit of Open Science	8
Theme 1: "I had no idea"	8
Theme 2: Safe Engagement at Open Seeds	9
Theme 3: Open Seeds does not break siloed work	11
3.2. Second overarching theme: Elephants in the room	12
Theme 4: Soil is not fertile for open seeds	12
Theme 5: Open Science and Open Seeds end up reproducing social inequities and power imbalances.	15
4. Discussion	17
Possible avenues for improvement	20
Conclusion	21
Credit authorship contribution statement	22
Declaration of competing interest	22
Acknowledgments	22
References	23

Abstract

Open Science practices, despite their potential benefits, are not widely adopted. Many researchers lack familiarity or skills to implement them effectively, highlighting a need for structured training. The purpose of this qualitative study was to explore the impact of a cohort-based Open Science training and mentoring programme called Open Seeds on the research projects and practices of mentors and mentees. Adopting a social constructionist paradigm, we conducted personal semi-structured interviews and one focus group session. We used a reflexive thematic analysis approach to find patterns related to participants' accounts of the impact Open Seeds had on their lives as researchers, what they believed were missed opportunities for impact, and also their ideas of Open Science in their particular contexts. The Open Seeds programme showed positive but limited impact. Practices found to be effective included creating safe participation spaces marked by a culture of kindness, while those found to be in need of improvement included collaborative practices amongst Open Seeds participants. Some key barriers to Open Science adoption in research were found to be overlooked, possibly hindering potential long-term impact. These include competitiveness, pervasive mental health challenges, inequities in resource and time availability, lack of institutional incentives, and politics. The study reveals a broader tension between innovative goals and traditional practice, emphasising the need for community-wide efforts to achieve Open Science objectives. These findings can inform improvements to Open Seeds and other Open Science training programmes.

1. Introduction

Open Science has been described as both a set of research methods, tools, platforms and practices, and a research reform movement aiming at making academic research more transparent, accessible, reliable, and inclusive. Open Science practices include open access to publications, open data, open source software, process transparency through pre-registration and pre-prints, open methods, and citizen science (Cole et al., 2024). It also includes issues such as pursuing replication studies, and re-evaluating institutional incentives (Bertram et al., 2023). Importantly, Open Science maintains a strong continuity with values long viewed as key to science: critical questioning, search for reliable evidence, and public debate (Leonelli, 2023). However, and as emphasised by UNESCO (2021), Open Science goes over traditional science by opening the processes of scientific knowledge creation beyond the traditional scientific community and by increasing scientific collaborations and information sharing for the benefit of science and society.

In this study we understand traditional science to be characterised by a culture that is hierarchical, competitive, commercialised, and self-referential (Leonelli, 2023). The Open Science movement's attempts to break from traditional science can be seen as a response to broad transformations brought about by the digitalisation, globalisation and commodification of research (Leonelli, 2023). This response has also been precipitated by evidence of non-replicable results across certain disciplines, and by a desire amongst researchers to move from the competitiveness based model towards collaborative research (Bertram et al., 2023; Leonelli, 2023). One key idea is that Open Science is better able to deal with complex societal problems such as climate change or global pandemics (Cole et al., 2024; Persic et al., 2021) and therefore produce more significant impact compared to traditional science research (Cole et al., 2024).

Despite its potential benefits, the adoption of Open Science practices is not widespread (Armeni et al., 2021). Many researchers are unfamiliar with Open Science practices, or lack the skills to implement them effectively (Ursić et al., 2024), which points to a need for training to allow researchers to implement Open Science practices into their work (Kohrs et al., 2023). One example of such training is Open Seeds, a 16-week cohort-based mentoring and training programme for researchers interested in applying open science principles in their work and becoming Open Science ambassadors in their communities. Open Seeds is a flagship programme by Open Life Science (OLS), a non-profit organisation that has delivered two rounds of cohort-based training per year since early 2020, training over 500 people with the support of more than 200 mentors, experts, and facilitators. OLS's original curriculum materials were based on the materials and interaction styles of the Mozilla Open Leaders initiative (*Mozilla Open Leaders*, n.d.). OLS has a worldwide reach and aims to make research accessible, inclusive, and equitable for everyone.

Understanding the impact of these Open Science educational interventions can help organisers assess the effectiveness of their strategies in transforming research culture (Kohrs et al., 2023). To the best of our knowledge there have been no studies interrogating the impact of Open Science training programs similar to Open Seeds. A recent review of the impact of programs that integrate open and reproducible scholarship into teaching and learning found that high-quality, in-depth studies in this area are sparse, and mostly limited to student surveys (Pownall et al., 2023). Open Seeds does not follow up with participants beyond the post-cohort survey to gauge further growth or hindrances to the adoption of the practices taught in the programme.

This qualitative study attempts to answer what has been the impact of Open Seeds on the careers of some of its mentors and mentees, in order to improve future interventions. Initially the research question pertained only the actual impact, but throughout the process and in view of the data, the question evolved to include expected impacts, the structural issues that make open practices difficult to adopt,

and what programs like Open Seeds could do to tackle those problems. A qualitative approach, as described in the method section, was chosen to access the depth that could not be reached solely via post cohort graduation surveys (*Welcome to OLS Stats — OLS Stats*, n.d.).

2. Methods

2.1. Approach to the research

Adopting a social constructionist paradigm as its epistemological stance, this qualitative study used a reflexive thematic analysis approach (Braun & Clarke, 2022) to analyse data generated through 17 semi-structured personal interviews and one Focus Group with five participants. Constructionism poses the premise that research practices produce rather than reveal data (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The **social constructionist paradigm** challenges the idea that knowledge is based upon objective, unbiased observation of the world; it invites us to be critical of the idea that our observations unproblematically show us the actual nature of the world (Burr, 2015). We understand knowledge to be historically and culturally constructed, situated and tied to human practices (Braun & Clarke, 2022). The **reflexive thematic analysis** approach was used to find patterns of meaning across the dataset. As part of this process, an inductive orientation to data analysis was chosen to generate the code labels and do the analysis. The inductive approach specifies that coding and theme development are driven by the data content and not by existing theories (deductive) as lenses through which we interpret the data (inductive and deductive orientations) can be a continuum, not necessarily a dichotomy.

Braun and Clarke (2019, 2021) add the adjective “reflexive” to their approach to thematic analysis (TA), and consider it a differentiating factor across versions of TA, because it values the “reflexive” researcher, one that is situated and aware, as an essential characteristic of thematic analysis. In reflexive TA, reflexivity involves the practice of critical reflection on our roles as researchers, on the research practices and process. Researchers are seen as situated interpreters of meaning, subjective storytellers. Subjectivity is therefore valued, instead of dreaded. But for reflexivity to be an asset it has to involve critically interrogating what is done, how and why, and the influence all this has on our research. The fully qualitative research paradigm (or “Big Q” framework) that informed this research differs in broad characteristics from a quantitative one, and provides the foundation for reflexive TA, giving the concepts and processes their logic and validity (Braun & Clarke, 2022). In reflexive TA the purpose of getting data from a small group of participants is to gain rich, in-depth understanding. Therefore smaller groups (samples) are valued. The data analysis focuses on text and meaning, and then on finding patterns of meaning. A reflexive

TA analysis aims to contribute to knowledge, knowing that it is only a part of a rich group of understandings.

Therefore, in this study knowledge generation is considered as inherently subjective, with the researcher always shaping what knowledge is produced, the questions asked, the reading of the data. Researchers are not like farmers harvesting crops, but like makers, creating something with tools, techniques and cultural resources. Thus the importance of reflecting, throughout the research, about the researcher's subjectivity and how it impacted the generation and reading of the data. The first author Paz Bernaldo (PB), who conducted the interviews, the Focus Group, and the analysis, worked as OLS's Open Seeds Coordinator from cohorts 6 to 8. This role in the organisation gave the researcher not only a close look at the inner workings of the programme, but her actions helped shape parts of what people experienced during these cohorts. Some of the other authors are or were also part of the OLS team. Working from this perspective, we tried to understand participants' perceptions about the impact (if any) that participating in Open Seeds had on their lives as researchers, the expected future impact, influencing factors, and their ideas about Open Science in general.

Two main practices helped with reflexivity: writing analytic memos during the first stage of the process and taking reflexivity notes after interviews. Reflexivity notes were used to critically reflect upon how the first author shaped the research process (with the first author being and working from outside academic institutions, having been particularly interested in inequities in science over the past 7 years, and not having conducted reflexive thematic analysis before). The second and third authors (GPI and YY) served as critical eyes on the theme development process. The other co-authors also facilitated a critical reflection on the final themes.

2.2. Participants

The two main criteria for taking part in the study were having graduated from the programme (in the case of mentees), or having mentored a project that graduated (in the case of mentors). For the Focus Group the selection criteria was geographic representation, having been a mentor or having graduated from Open Seeds.

All participants from cohorts OLS-1 (held in 2020) to OLS-7 (held in 2023) that met these criteria were contacted by the first author via email. The invitation email contained a PDF with an information sheet and a consent form, including detailed information about data management (anonymisation, storage). An open call for participants was also published in OLS's Slack workspace by the first author. A total of 21 people participated in the study and, out of those, five were invited by PB to participate in the Focus Group. In total, out of the 21 participants, 17 participated in personal interviews and 5 in the Focus Group (with one person participating in both).

Participants were living in four continents (South America, Europe, Africa, Asia), 37% of them were nationals from Europe. Eight participants were living in countries different from the countries they are nationals of. Sixteen identified as women and five as men. Ages ranged from 20 to 50 and represented 11 different research fields or disciplines (categorisation according to *Disciplines Covered by the Endorsing Bodies for Science, Engineering, Humanities, Social Science and Medicine*, n.d.). Six participants had not interacted with PB in her role as Cohort Coordinator, and first met her during their interviews. Eight participants had been both mentees and mentors, in different cohorts. Two participants who had been mentors had not been mentees. All interviewees were involved in practising research, directly doing research work, and/or in related roles, such as teaching, training, or data management. Most of the participants were working inside academia, but some were working in the private sector, and in nonprofit science organisations. Most of them had completed PhDs, some were university professors, and a couple had recently graduated from a masters program.

2.3. Data generation

Two data generation methods were used: 1) virtual, semi-structured, individual interviews; and 2) a virtual Focus Group. Most participants were assigned to individual interviews (17), while five participants joined the Focus Group.

Interviews were conducted online via Zoom, Whereby or Jitsi (according to the participant's preference) by the first author. They lasted from 68 minutes to 120 minutes (average time of 94 min), for a combined total of 23 hours of interview time, and were conducted either in English (13 interviews) or in Spanish (four interviews), according to the interviewee's preference. The Focus Group was led by the first author in English via Zoom. The interviews and Focus Group audios were recorded, and were transcribed verbatim by the main author. Those conducted in English were transcribed with the aid of Otter.ai and later checked against the original recording to correct errors and ensure accuracy. The interviews in Spanish were transcribed manually.

A semi-structured interview guide, which included a list of questions (available in a supplemental file) and probes, was used for the interviews. The latter focused on how Open Seeds had affected interviewees' research work and/or life, and what Open Science means in their own contexts and/or in general. Some common questions addressed in the interviews included: why do you think Open Science is important in your context? How did the idea of the project come about? What has happened with your project after Open Seeds?

2.4. Data analysis

The reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019, 2022) approach was used to identify patterns within the data, addressing the impact Open Seeds participants experienced as a result of their involvement in the program, and the influencing factors. The dataset was composed of all the written transcripts of the interviews and the Focus Group. Before the interviews and Focus Group took place, nine analytic memos were written by the first author exploring reflexive thematic analysis as an approach and the data management plan. These memos were reviewed by two people who are part of the OLS community but not employed by OLS. One of the memo reviewers had relevant experience in qualitative research while the second did not. The first author conducted the thematic analysis, after which, OLS staff members and other members from the wider OLS community, discussed and reviewed the findings. We used an inductive orientation to data, locating the analysis within the data content, in order for coding and theme development to be driven by the data content (and not guided by existing theory). The analysis explored meaning both semantically (at the explicit or manifest level) but also latently (at an underlying or implicit level). Because of the inductive approach, the first author did not map out the literature beforehand. She reviewed papers related to reflexive thematic analysis before data generation, but the actual engagement with literature related to the data came after theme development.

After transcription, the process of data familiarisation started. This process involved reading and re-reading the data. This familiarisation process allowed a first interpretation of the data. After this, the first author coded the data manually by highlighting significant phrases or paragraphs that seemed related to the research question, and making notes. Then came a second round of coding, also done manually, which involved getting rid of some codes, adding new ones or refining them.

It was during this coding process that the initial research question evolved to include not only actual impacts but the expected ones. This part involved printing all codes and all matching data extracts, cutting all extracts and codes and separately grouping similar codes to place them in a wall, physically moving the cut out (of extracts and code) together for better visual overview. Codes that represented similar meanings were condensed into one code. All codes and their data extracts were gathered in a separate document. This document (supplementary material S3) was used to cluster codes and thus develop candidate themes. This is the point, according to Braun & Clarke (2022), at which the scale in focus is shifted from the micro scope of the coding process towards the macro scale, exploring connections that might develop into broader patterns of meaning. Initially, eleven candidate themes were generated, which were then merged and reduced to five themes in the refinement stage. Two overarching themes were created to help explain the relationships between the themes. Reflexive thematic analysis can report patterned

meaning at three different levels: overarching themes, themes and subthemes. In this study, only overarching themes and themes are used. Overarching themes are like umbrella concepts under which we find a number of themes. They should demonstrate a broader concept that anchors themes together. A theme, on the other hand, captures multi-faceted manifestations of a single concept from the dataset, and is the key analytic unit in reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2021).

2.5 Ethics

Ethical approval was obtained from Pearl IRB (Indianapolis, Indiana, USA). When first invited to participate in the study, participants were sent an Informed Consent form, which came with an information sheet that included all relevant information about logistics, procedures, privacy and data management. All participants were adults from 20 to 50 years of age, and signed the consent form before the interviews and Focus Group took place. At the beginning of interviews or the Focus Group, but before the recording was started, participants answered some demographic questions, the Informed Consent form was read, questions from participants were answered, and participants were reminded they could end the interview or leave the Focus Group session at any point without giving any reasons. They were also made aware that the transcripts would be analysed and that data would be anonymised in order to open them up after the paper is published. Additional details about anonymisation procedures are available as supplementary materials.

The audio files will be destroyed when the final version of this manuscript is published, as agreed with participants in the Informed Consent Form. De-identified and anonymised data transcripts are shared openly under CC-BY 4.0 License for anyone to use on Zenodo when the paper is published as a preprint. More information on what data is shared openly and how we secure its anonymity is available as supplemental materials.

3. Results

Overall, five themes were created from our analysis of the dataset, which includes the written transcripts of all the interviews and the Focus Group, organised into two overarching themes which we analyse in the next section: (1) The pursuit of Open Science, and (2) Elephants in the room.

3.1. First overarching theme: The pursuit of Open Science

This overarching theme includes three themes that capture the participants' views on the program's curriculum, the style of communication, and the type of interactions that occurred when going through the program. Participants' accounts depicted

Open Seeds as distinct from traditional science in certain ways, while also resembling it in others.

Theme 1: “I had no idea”

This theme captures a common element of surprise in participants' accounts **in relation to the contents of the program**. The participants' initial goals were mostly centred around their individual projects, but the topics included in the Open Seeds curriculum turned into unexpected and positive learnings. In one case, for instance, such a thing was understanding the culture within Open Science communities, in other, a very specific topic that had never crossed their minds:

“So in terms of technical or skill wise, I don't think, it's not, it didn't meet that kind of goal. But we got something we didn't expect (...) the culture within the Open Science community, that's something we got.” [206]

“The allyship was a topic I never really thought about, and I never thought that it'd be useful to me, but then there's kind of a nice surprise I think.” [313]

The level of surprise varied, but all participants felt that had it not been for their involvement in the programme, they would have not paid attention to things that they now deem to be indeed important for practising Open Science. They appreciated tools, topics, and general learnings they considered irrelevant or less relevant before Open Seeds.

“Then, I also learned a lot about - and I am putting it into practice - how to build communities. I don't think community building is considered important when you have a project, but it is super important.” [167]

“All this stuff about communities and community building was completely new for me because, in my previous environment, nobody really cared about it. It was more about some interesting individual achievements.” [264]

The Open Seeds curriculum strongly emphasises community building and community engagement, and interviewees indeed perceived this to be one key focus. Interviewees kept comparing their experience in Open Seeds to their experience in laboratories, and research groups, and would often refer to themselves as becoming less “individualistic” after joining Open Seeds.

“The community aspect stood out to me a lot, and it's still a highlight from the cohort calls.” [272]

“There is safe peer learning [in communities like Open Seeds]. And I think that helps in accelerating skills, the soft skills or tech skills. So I really like this aspect of community [work]” [345]

“But then also I wanted to continue learning more, I wanted to understand how to build communities, as I was now part of the co-founders of [org name], so I really needed this information. So I started volunteering more in OLS.” [406]

This theme shows that the topics emphasised in Open Seeds, like community building, community engagement and allyship, were unexpected but nevertheless positively valued.

Theme 2: Safe Engagement at Open Seeds

This theme focuses on the participants' positive evaluation, not of the specific contents of the program, but of the style of their interactions with others as part of Open Seeds: OLS staff members, mentors, experts, facilitators, fellow mentees, fellow mentors, and former cohort participants.

Participants talked about the Open Seeds/OLS culture and defined it as kind and approachable. They felt cared for and appreciated, different from what many have experienced in traditional science, where they feel competition and individualism are commonplace. Open Seeds worked as a place for acceptance and kindness. Those who were there to help participants were not only knowledgeable but also approachable:

"Interpersonal relationships were much less toxic there than I expected, like what I was used to. And I just, at first, I couldn't understand what was happening. It was like, why is everybody so nice? Like what?!" [263]

"It's cool that at OLS people are put first." [155]

Many accounts detailed that at Open Seeds the ways to communicate were as important as the contents. Even interviewees who had participated in the first cohorts mentioned how things were communicated within Open Seeds. Many of them said they had adopted OLS-style practices in their day-to-day jobs teaching students or doing research with teams:

"I think one big thing I still use to this day is the gratitude ritual. Which was useful. And I think it frames things in quite a nice way and builds up this trust and mentor-mentee relationship." [193]

"And with the mentor, we would have to find a GIF of what represents our week and we talked about how our week went and that kind of thing, which I liked, because I also had a teaching post, before coming to [country]. And I wanted to create that kind of environment with my students because I wanted them to relax before starting the lecture." [210]

"The style of managing projects and keeping people going and engaged and being responsive [...] the main thing is that it helps me run projects now." [382]

Another relevant and frequently mentioned aspect of their relationships with others was the lack of hierarchies. Participants frequently described mentors as kind, respectful, resourceful, and friendly equals:

"When I see my interactions with my supervisor or in academia I think the relationship was just like, ok, this is the big man and just we're like an empty glass of

water. He's the one supposed to fill the glass with water but with my mentor in OLS, things were different. It was really a kind of friendly relationship that I couldn't have with my supervisor.” [141]

With the help of their mentors, Open Seeds participants felt encouraged to iterate, consider new perspectives and redesign their projects, something they described as unusual, positive, and motivating. As mentioned before, interviewees were either practising scientists or were somehow involved in research, so trial and error processes are not new to them. However, they mentioned facing institutional constraints to experimentation and bringing in new practices. Open Seeds allowed them a different space for experimentation (“free-flowing” [329]):

“So those kinds of interactions were very, very constructive (...) we came with a vision, and during the program, we changed the vision of the problem of our project, due to interaction and exchanges with people and so on.” [136]

“It's something I appreciate very much from OLS, continuous learning, and then also restoring faith in how science is working because sometimes I see things and I'm very discouraged.” [129]

“The first one was where I really understood the power of mentorship. Really, at my work, I do have mentors. However, the work I do is also time-bound and there is funding involved in all of that. So we have to, I mean, we have to have certain very focused targets or goals to complete and within a certain timeframe. However, [with Open Seeds] was more free-flowing, because it was a volunteer project. It was free-flowing.” [329]

This theme shows that, by centering on a kind and approachable culture, Open Seeds/OLS is distancing from a traditional scientific system perceived as individualist and competitive.

Theme 3: Open Seeds does not break siloed work

This theme explores how the practice of Open Science within the program took place. Many accounts expressed the need for participants to interact in more substantial ways during the program. Similarly to traditional science, it was hard for them to look for and find collaborators, and when it happened, it was without the mediation of the program.

“There is maybe I don't know exactly what OLS can do, but there is this need for the cohorts, the different cohorts to interact.” [158]

“So I think there is this need to create bonds between the cohorts so that people can interact and build this sense of community.” [160]

“I did have a thought about that. I think we didn't have a lot of time to interact with other teams. I think the only time I really got to know, I mean, to know what everyone was really doing was the last call where people were presenting their projects and all that stuff.” [367]

Almost all interviewees stated they had not stayed in touch with their mentors/mentees after their cohort ended. Most of them have gone back to Slack (the communication app/platform used by OLS) once in a while, when wanting to share information, ask something, or someone tags them. Many participants finished the program not having met new colleagues or collaborators, and not having established a long-term relationship with their mentors:

“After OLS most of it, we did learn a lot, but sometimes we didn't get, let me not say we but I personally didn't get a lot of collaborations with other teams that were in OLS.” [376]

“Because if I talked about community, I would think about interacting with peers, but I interact mostly with my mentor and lecture so it feels more like a mentoring program to me.” [220]

“(…) but what's missing, above all, is connecting communities like long term, and overall, because it's, I think it kind of works quite often. That community just stays in a bubble, and does not join projects in other communities very often, and if it's connected, it's not connected by one person or something.” [389]

Overall, this overarching theme reveals a tension within Open Seeds. On one hand, the program presents a non-traditional curriculum, and a culture of safe and horizontal engagement, separating itself from traditional science which emphasises technical contents, individualism and competitiveness. On the other hand, despite these efforts, some participants were not able to substantially collaborate out of their usual “silos”.

3.2. Second overarching theme: Elephants in the room

This second overarching theme includes the participants' accounts on what they perceive as key issues for the implementation of Open Science, but that may not be addressed by the Open Seeds program. Interviewees spoke about structural barriers that interfere with Open Science practice, and also expressed that in many ways Open Science organisations (including OLS) end up reproducing some of the same problems. Also, some of them described actions that could be taken in order to address some of these neglected issues.

Theme 4: Soil is not fertile for open seeds

Participants described facing many barriers to practising and advocating for Open Science in their institutions. This theme explores limitations that were not perceived within Open Seeds, but are instead external to the program, or even structural issues in research or academia.

Participants' accounts depicted Open Science being still unclear to most people working in science, making it hard for them to advocate for it in their workplaces. One of the interviewees, for instance, admitted not having considered bringing Open

Science as an issue to her colleagues, despite being someone who actively participates in more than one Open Science community:

“[About Open Science] I generally feel like there are people who do not necessarily know what it means and how it impacts the science that they do. Yeah, but a few people, me and [name of colleague] who was also part of [name of the Open Science community], do know about it. I think we should do a better job at advocating for it here [their workplace].” [416]

Many participants expressed that collaboration is a big part of the changes they want to see happening, but that competition is currently the rule in science, and not the exception:

“The issue for me is like we tend to compete with one another in science and everyone wants to keep their project secret.” [214] “Right now even in our own groups, we are still competing and keeping secrets and so I guess it’s normal. Around here. Yeah” [216].

“Academic positions are very competitive and I read Twitter, and it’s like, you publish in Nature and Science and you still get kicked out of academia and an academic job becomes very stressful and that’s why I don’t know, I think that’s the part that makes people become very competitive.” [217]

“And also these other people were doing the same things and then now try to create a network whereby it’s not about competition, but it’s more progressive research.” [373]

The idea that the scientific career is one marked by stress, resulting in part from such competitiveness, was present in many of the interviews. Being burned out was described as a common, persistent, and growing problem. The causes of being stressed and burned out in science are systemic, according to these accounts.

“I think more people are burned out. I think more people are experiencing work stress to the point that it’s affected their mental health and physical health.” [203]

“During school years, and during college, like it can be very competitive, it can be even toxic at times. And like, it can take a toll on your mental health and stuff.” [421]

Time was a recurrent issue in many of the interviews. It was described and experienced as an extremely important yet very often lacking resource. Time is considered as a resource that is not given the value it has for science, and not only for individual researchers’ purposes but for collective purposes as well, as described by the following account:

“To work on the mentoring or the mentee stuff is critical. I think this, especially for mentees who may be quite busy, they might be in an early stage of their career and have to do things outside of their normal working hours or have to take extra time on top of their working hours. So finding a way to address that would be great.” [202]

Time is used by the scientific system for productivity, for competitiveness, but denied for other aspects of being or becoming a scientist. How time is valued is a systemic issue:

“Yeah, I think it's one that comes up time and time again and what we do and that's time, time, mentors not having time, mentees not having time. This idea of protected time is such an important one. Being able to take time out of your working hours.”
[201]

Time availability for research was also described as unevenly distributed, depending on whether someone works in a context with abundant science resources, on where in the country they work, if in the capital city or a smaller city, or the size of their host institution:

“Here we have like eight to 12 hours of classes per week. So it's too much. In this sense, I think you will get the sense that it's hard to compare with professors who live in the Global North because they have like two hours a week of classes and the rest of the time they do research. I can't compare against that, not even a bit.” [221]

A common challenge for individual researchers across different countries was being assessed according to the number of publications, especially publications in high impact journals. This interviewee from the previous quote also felt time availability limited their ability to produce enough papers, and was therefore at a disadvantage when competing for resources or scientific prestige.

Time is also necessary for learning new skills. Interviewees referred that having limited time availability hindered their ability to learn the tools required to practise Open Science, which decreased their opportunities to engage in open collaborations:

“Nobody is on GitHub here. I know a bit. Just a little. I do have to take more chances to use GitHub, I think it's a very strong tool. It's very good. But since it's not intuitive, you have to take some time to learn. You cannot just go there and use it and [expect it to be] fine.” [236]

Interviewees also linked their ability to dedicate time to practise or advocate for Open Science to the availability of resources in their institutions. Participants working in low resource contexts felt that when there is time and funding, they need to cover the essentials first:

“We barely talk about Open Science, but I think we have... So let me tell you a little about my university (...) as a young public University, we still have to build the research, we have to build the laboratories. So I think that we are all at least most of us are prone to [practising] Open Science. We just need time to do it.” [225-226]

The idea that there are essentially no good institutional incentives for doing Open Science was emphasised by a few participants. This lack of concrete incentives, paired with a lack of understanding or misunderstanding of how the Open Science

systems work, might result in people feeling fearful or suspicious of what “the end game” [120] of Open Science is, who benefits, who loses, and why:

“I mean, nowadays, the fact you share all the data, in real-time, you don’t know if someone is going to copy you, and who values that I’m doing my stuff openly? Nobody does” [309]

“For me, the problem is that there are no mechanisms that reward Open Science (...) So, there is this perverse system in which there are no rewards.” [307]

Some interviewees reflected about politics in their local contexts having a huge influence in what happens in science systems at different levels. To them, it matters who is in government, and what their priorities and political ideas are, because ultimately whether they get funding depends on the “the politics and politicians that give us money to work” [228]. One of the accounts describes how they do not like reading Global North journals in their field, because they “are always trying not to talk about politics” [232]. In their specific case, political goodwill is the “biggest barrier” to their scientific work [237]. These accounts emphasise how important it can be to include the issue of politics in the discussions around Open Science - not only Open Science-specific policies, but also general science policies and politics. Some interviewees summarised their struggle as being a consequence of capitalism:

“How can we make Open Science more open if we don't talk about politics, because science career is very capitalist, too much” [234].

“It'd be awesome if we could get rid of capitalism” [291].

This theme captured the many barriers to practising and advocating for Open Science that participants face outside Open Science communities. They feel they might be able to address some of them, such as the unfamiliarity with this movement. Most of these hurdles, however, are perceived as too entrenched and unsurmountable, such as competitiveness, pervasive mental health issues, inequities in time and resource availability, lack of incentives, and politics, as shown in the quotes above.

Theme 5: Open Science and Open Seeds end up reproducing social inequities and power imbalances.

Interviewees also discussed other issues that make it difficult for the Open Science movement to live up to the principles and values it centers. In contrast to what was included in the previous theme, these accounts refer to what happens within Open Seeds and the broader Open Science movement in general. They relate to what Open Science organisations do, or not do, to address those issues, and therefore, end up, maybe inadvertently, replicating shortcomings of traditional science.

Some accounts critique Open Science organisations to promote or hold values and principles they do not really fully follow. The frustration expressed by these

interviewees imply that declaring people have the ability to practice Open Science when they do not, such as when their challenges are big and complex, or when the trade offs are huge, might be detrimental for the actual goal of advancing Open Science:

“There is so much talk [among Open Science organisations] about values, mission, vision, and how pretty everything is. But all these beautiful things don’t always turn into practice. The right efforts aren’t there, because there are actors that have a lot of resources to get this [Open Science] to reach more people.” [289-290]

“OLS always has a book or article at hand they use as a base to create this or that thing, and that is alright, but there is a big distance sometimes with the reality. Not always [reading] it all means you’ll practise it or make the effort to try to reach that ideal.” [293]

“I mean, for instance, people from least developed countries that participate in OLS, theoretically can have access to the same resources as the rest of us. But it doesn’t work that way in practice, right? They face a lot more barriers and just by saying that they are doing Open Science and have access does not solve the problem.” [284]

According to one account, the inequities in access to resources mentioned in the previous theme, also exist within Open Science organisations or communities, as one interviewee expressed:

“I was never naive about these issues, but now I see them in practice, I see how the inequalities stay the same, even within organisations that have the best intentions.” [215]

“[among Open Science organisations or groups] there are a lot of money disputes, for financing, for opportunities.” [281]

Many accounts described English being the *de facto* language of science as a key obstacle for the equity and equality principles of Open Science, and for programs like Open Seeds to have an impact outside privileged groups. This is clearly illustrated by the fact that some interviewees said they could not recommend Open Seeds to colleagues or students, simply because it was not available in their local language:

“[In academia] it is assumed English to be the language people need to know better, and that is also assumed at OLS. Despite having people from different countries. That is something we need to discuss more as a society, as a scientific community.” [296]

“So I did like the project [Open Seeds] a lot. I hope it grows, but I don’t know. I have some ideas of how it could be [inaudible] but the language is always a barrier because I can speak English, I have to practise, I know, but I can speak English and they [their previous team] can understand English, but I cannot recommend the project to many people, you know.” [222]

“When the project [Open Seeds] is all English based, and those people are gonna say no, they’re not going to be able to do it.” [116]

One interviewee offered some advice on how OLS could tackle these language-related inequities, and therefore avoid reproducing them, by providing training and mentoring in local languages:

“So when the project [Open Seeds] is all English based, and those people are gonna say no, they're not going to be able to do it. (...) if we had like communities, paying for the Latino community and for the Portuguese community, and we're not gonna have a lot of projects, we don't need to solve everyone's problems at the same time. Let's take three projects in Portuguese with three mentors, and get them to evolve this relationship to work on the project but also to be able to present in English after one year of the program. Something like that. And this could be more of a long-term thing.” [116]

Many accounts detailed how the push for open access to data and publications contributes to these inequities. They also claim that this topic is usually only shallowly discussed, limited to open access licences or paywalls. One of the interviewees, however, provided a rich depiction of how complex and multifaceted this issue is, relating the topic of “scooping” to those of language barriers, the inequity of resources, and incentives:

“In my former university, [I] feel people just have a very naive concept of Open Science, which is open publishing. Have you opened the paper? Published your data? And when they hear that, they already think “oh they're going to steal my data!”, which is a worry for them because some of them do a lot of locally based, regional based research, which probably took them a lot of time, a lot of effort and they have been doing that for 30 or 20 years. So when someone publishes something on that topic openly, someone from North America can just take the data and publish something in Nature, while they are publishing in regional journals because they are just taking their time to publish (...) So I feel like this is a conversation that we need to have. I feel people that are using open data sometimes come from a more privileged background, that have access to English training and a lot of things while people that are doing a lot of local research, a lot of fieldwork and putting in a lot of efforts, are not recognized in the same way because academia privileges who publishes in high impact journals.” [119]

This theme includes, similarly to what was shown in Theme 3 (“Open Seeds does not break siloed work”), issues in which Open Science organisations fail to live up to the values they advocate for. In this case, interviewees’ accounts not only imply the lack of a potential positive impact, but suggest that Open Science, as practised today, can indeed be detrimental. In contrast to what we saw with the previous theme, statements suggest that a lot more can be done by organisations such as OLS involved in Open Science training.

4. Discussion

This study explored Open Seeds participants’ experiences with the program, the impact it had on their work/lives, on the Open Science movement, and their relation

with traditional academia. As pointed out by Kohrs et al (2023), studies of the impact of educational programs in Open Science are sparse, and are mostly based on standard course evaluation surveys (Pownall et al., 2023). Our in-depth analysis sheds light not only on the impact and limitations of Open Seeds, but also on the barriers that this and other Open Science programs and their participants face when attempting to practise or advocate for Open Science.

The first overarching theme, *The pursuit of Open Science*, portrays participants' accounts in relation to the efforts made by Open Seeds towards its goal of training researchers as Open Science practitioners and ambassadors. The first theme, "I had no idea", showed how participants found something unexpected in Open Seeds. One possible reason for this surprise could be the widespread lack of awareness about what Open Science is (Funamori, 2017; Armeni et al, 2021), or the fact that there is no one single definition about Open Science or consensus about what Open Science includes (Albornoz et al., 2018; Fecher and Friesike, 2014). UNESCO (2021) recently published a set of recommendations on open science which include what they call an "internationally agreed definition" of Open Science. OLS, however, does not provide a single explicit definition of what Open Science is. Instead, OLS references the varied definitions provided by UNESCO, OECD (Making Open Science a Reality, 2015) and others in their training resources. OLS also shares their own vision for Open Science on their website home page: "we imagine a future where research is accessible, inclusive, and equitable for everyone" (*Open Science* | OLS, n.d.). In Open Seed's onboarding presentation for each cohort, the OLS team states: "we believe that to be effective, science should be shared openly with others and made freely available" (OLS, 2021). Together with the curriculum's strong emphasis on the participatory nature of Open Science, this indicates that the Open Science definition implicitly favoured by OLS might be closer to what Fecher and Friesike (2014) call "Pragmatic School", which posits that the goal of Open Science is to make the process of knowledge creation more efficient and goal oriented by favouring collaboration. These authors do not claim a consistently clear-cut distinction between the five schools, and indeed we see some coincidences with the "public" and "infrastructure" schools, the first of which promotes accessibility in terms of participation and research comprehensibility, the latter focusing on the technical infrastructure that enables emerging research practices, software tools, applications, and computing networks. Another possible reason for this pattern of surprise observed in the first theme could be that the topics favoured by Open Seeds (community engagement, collaboration, project design and management) felt new and/or refreshing. Currently, technical skills (related to data management and reproducibility), tools and infrastructure are often emphasised (in line with the "Infrastructure School" of Open Science). Because participants join the program with their projects and have expectations about the skills or tools they need for them, it is likely they were expecting a stronger focus on the technical skills for openness.

In regards to the second theme, *Safe Engagement at Open Seeds*, the analysis posits that participants valued positively both the program contents focused on community building *and* the style of communication and the resulting human interactions in Open Seeds, suggesting that they might also endorse the definition of Open Science adopted by OLS. A common thread in analyses of the neoliberal university is the lack of space for the human or personal aspect of science (Burton, 2021). It is therefore not surprising that Open Seeds participants, most of them coming from experiences of unkindness in academia, would appreciate a different atmosphere in Open Seeds, one in which people “are put first”, together with the focus on the participatory and community aspect of Open Science. It should be nonetheless considered that participants’ unanimous positive accounts on these topics might have been influenced by a selection bias: those interviewed as part of this study were Open Seeds graduates (overall, 94% of participants graduated the program), thus leaving out the 6% of participants who might have left the program due to conflicts or disagreements with the program’s content or approach. Also, all interviewees had voluntarily agreed to be interviewed, which could also select for those willing to give positive feedback. However, the fact that these interviewees provided critical feedback in other topics suggests that their positive opinions on this topic might not be a result of this bias. A set of recommendations for short-format training for scientists has been recently published (Williams et al., 2023), and based on our analysis, we suggest that putting an emphasis explicitly on engaging community participants with kindness could be added to these recommendations.

Contemporary science is increasingly characterised by international collaborative research projects working across institutional and disciplinary boundaries, which are able to tackle complex and significant scientific goals (Dusdal & Powell, 2021). Open Science practices aim at fostering collaboration outside of the usual academic “silos”, favouring a “team science” approach (Thibault et al., 2023). Despite the strong focus of OLS in collaborating with groups and individuals in a number of initiatives (including bringing Open Seeds to life), and of Open Seeds on collaboration, the analysis showed that participants could not effectively put collaboration into practice during the program. Participants considered the mentor-mentee relationship established during the program as friendly and horizontal, and therefore different to the traditional supervisor-student relationship. However, the lack of a “team science” approach in establishing collaboration among all cohort participants means that Open Seeds ends up mimicking the traditional apprenticeship model of academia. According to Thibault et al. (2023), this outcome can be considered an “outdated vestige” that hinders the implementation of several open practices. Open Seeds centers collaboration as a cornerstone of Open Science, but is not effective at fostering it amongst participants who join from different geographical locations and with their own projects. This reveals a tension between theory and practice, similar to what has been observed in other organisations that promote openness (Langlois, 2022). Tackling the practice of collaboration through explicit actions would be consistent with Open Seeds’ goals,

and complementary of its current focus on promoting kind and healthy research practices. Scientific collaborations as seen in team science approaches allow a division of labour in ways that might reduce the workload for each individual, which is a known barrier to adopting Open Science related skills and frameworks (Hostler, 2023).

The second overarching theme, *Elephants in the Room*, includes key issues which seem to be overlooked by organisations that promote Open Science. Many of those are structural barriers that are extensively acknowledged by Open Science related literature, and recognised by many Open Science practitioners (Bertram et al., 2023; Gagliardi et al., 2015; Gownaris et al., 2022; Leonelli, 2023). Despite good intentions by individual researchers and organisations like OLS, our analysis showed that these obstacles to practising Open Science appear to be pervasive and difficult to circumvent. However, published guidelines on how to implement Open Science practices in research institutions consider some of these problems and suggest ways to address them (Kohrs et al., 2023). We believe these structural barriers should be acknowledged, discussed and understood by organisations that train people in Open Science frameworks and practices, as well as funders and policy makers.

Some of those key issues were shown to be present also within Open Seeds, as depicted in the last theme, *Open Science and Open Seeds end up reproducing social inequities and power imbalances*. This theme adds evidence to the existence of a tension within the program, between theory and practice, between disruptive and traditional science.

Possible avenues for improvement

Open Seeds involves mid- and post-cohort surveys to invite feedback from participants to understand their experiences and implement changes in both curriculum and delivery process. In contrast to the cohort-specific survey data, the in-depth qualitative data presented in this study will help improve both the programmatic design and potential for the long-term impact of Open Seeds on its participants. Beyond Open Seeds, insights gained in this study could also help other Open Science initiatives in designing training interventions.

Many participants feel that OLS and similar organisations “push” to implement Open Science, without always being in a position to successfully address structural inequalities and barriers. OLS has tried to tackle some of these inequalities by implementing a microgrant programme for Open Seeds participants to cover basics such as internet connectivity costs, an approach that, although useful, might not be sufficient in the long term.

Openness operates differently for different individuals, and there is not a single way to learn openness but rather different ways to foster it (Roberts, 2020). Also, standardised Open Science practices can privilege some forms of inquiry over others (Leonelli, 2022). Open Seeds shares frameworks and a selected set of tools and

practices presented by invited speakers, which might not be adaptable to all participants' contexts. An alternative approach could be presenting not one framework with associated tools and practices, but a battery of frameworks that considers the structural barriers identified in this work, along with concrete examples of Open Science done in different contexts. Importantly, looking at critical views of Open Science could further healthy reflection and debate.

For some of the barriers, participants suggested concrete actions Open Seeds could take to address them. One of them is the role of Open Science organisations, especially those with a global presence, such as OLS, in the perpetuation of English as the dominant language of science. The prevalence of English in scientific communication and collaboration creates disparities among researchers from different regions (Ramírez-Castañeda, 2020). One suggestion to tackle this issue within Open Seeds was to run the program in different languages, focusing on fewer, selected projects, but for a longer period of time. The human resources needed for such a task are a huge limitation. This could be partially overcome by automated translation tools (Fiorini et al., 2023). Funders, however, rarely fund the delivery of training in different languages. Also, localisation to fit in different contexts and validation of translated text require significant human resources, the cost for which is often not covered by either traditional funding sources or the limited number of open science funding sources (Almarzouq et al). OLS has in the past tried to tackle some aspects of the language barrier. For instance, by matching mentees and mentors according to their preferred/primary language, by providing live translation in Spanish during one of the graduations, or having videos from the first three cohorts captioned in Arabic (*OLS-3-Talks*, n.d.). These past efforts might set a good precedent for adapting the design of the program in order to tackle the broader language barriers in a systematic way. These efforts beyond OLS will require policy makers and funders to join the table and invest in supporting multilingualism in (open) science.

As mentioned earlier, our results showed that participants could not always put collaboration into practice within the program, which could be tackled through the redesign of some of the program's activities. Currently, participants work on their own projects with their own mentor, and learn about other projects mostly during the graduation. One possible way to overcome this could be holding mentoring sessions for many teams simultaneously, encouraging the interaction between them. Group interactions like these would require, for example, that mentors facilitate in such a way that nobody monopolises the conversation and everyone gets to share their perspectives and progress. After this study was concluded, OLS hosted one of the largest groups: 110 participants in the ninth cohort of Open Seeds, where several mentors took 2 to 4 mentees, each working on similar but separate projects. The effectiveness of this format can later be assessed.

Open Seeds participants share about themselves and their projects on the OLS website, on a cohort-specific GitHub repository and on the Slack workspace maintained by the OLS team. However, these do not necessarily lead to participants

reaching out to each other organically. Mandatory weekly or fortnightly project updates with facilitated interactions on Slack could also help participants learn about and connect with each other asynchronously. These additional actions could help in breaking the traditional apprenticeship model of academia by favouring and valuing peer feedback, and could eventually allow for collaborative projects between groups to emerge.

The qualitative approach used in this study was useful to uncover issues that had not been found previously in the post-cohort surveys or in informal interactions with participants, allowing also for a more comprehensive understanding of the underlying factors at play. This evaluation, however, provided only a “snapshot”, which could easily become outdated if there are changes in the programme. We believe that incorporating a regular evaluation could provide valuable insights into the impact on the participants on a longer term, and could help in assessing the outcomes of the implementation of different activities or modifications in the curriculum, allowing for an iterative improvement of the program. We also consider that reaching participants that did not complete the Open Seeds programme, albeit difficult, should also be included in the evaluation strategy. Conducting impact evaluations is critical as they provide valuable insights and opportunities for open science training programmes and funding agencies to enhance effectiveness of the shared ecosystem, and of science as a whole.

Conclusion

Our analysis found the impact of the Open Seeds programme to have positive, but limited impact on its participants. A positive impact was found on the issues of interpersonal relationships, an aspect that was highly valued by participants. The approach to the implementation of collaborative practices within Open Seeds was found to be limited, participants did not effectively engage with each other or with each other’s projects. Several key issues known in traditional science that limit the adoption of open practices were considered to be overlooked, which can hinder a long-term impact of the program.

Results from this study should be taken into account in order to improve the Open Seeds programme's design. These recommendations could also help other Open Science initiatives in designing training interventions. Overall, this study exposes a tension between the goals of open science and traditional practices, which is not exclusive to OLS and Open Seeds, but a widespread issue in Open Science communities. This highlights the need for a concerted effort by the whole scientific ecosystem to realise the goals of Open Science.

OLS, through Open Seeds, works across geographies, languages, time zones, and disciplines. Implementing any successful programme in such a diverse context is difficult. But most importantly, working in this broad ecosystem allows us to see the

inequalities and tensions that ought to be seen and discussed by the Open Science community as a whole.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Paz Bernaldo: Conceptualisation, Data Curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Resources, Writing - original draft, Writing – review & editing
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3129-9020>

Gustavo Pereyra Irujo: Conceptualisation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2261-6928>

Yo Yehudi: Project Administration, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Supervision, Writing - review & editing. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2705-1724>

Anelda Van der Walt: Methodology, Writing - review & editing.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4245-8119>

Irene Ramos: Writing - review & editing. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3315-2281>

Bethan Iley: Writing - review & editing. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5813-3303>

Paz Miguez: Methodology. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1099-4347>

Esther Plomp: Writing - review & editing. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3625-1357>

Patricia Herterich: Writing - review & editing. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4542-9906>

Malvika Sharan: Conceptualisation, Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing, Project administration. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6619-7369>

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

Beth Duckles advised on early iterations of the study design. The following OLS community members proofread anonymised transcripts (and suggested additional anonymity-preserving edits), before public deposit: Hao Ye, Sabrina López, Bernard Kwame Solodzi, Riva Quiroga, Irene Ramos, Anelda van der Walt, Alexander Martínez Méndez, Nyasita Ondari.

This work was funded in part by a grant from the Wellcome Trust, grant number 223851/Z/21/Z, and in part by a grant from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative DAF, an advised fund of Silicon Valley Community Foundation.

Supplementary materials

Bernaldo, P., & OLS. (2025). Supporting materials for "Examining the impact and limitations of Open Science training: a case study of the "Open Seeds" programme" [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15024935>

S1	Anonymised transcripts - Word format
S2	Anonymised transcripts - PDF
S3	Coded data extracts
S4	All codes and themes
S5	Informed consent forms
S6	Participant profile (region of origin only)

References

- Armeni, K., Brinkman, L., Carlsson, R., Eerland, A., Fijten, R., Fondberg, R., Heininga, V. E., Heunis, S., Koh, W. Q., Masselink, M., Moran, N., Baoill, A. Ó., Sarafoglou, A., Schettino, A., Schwamm, H., Sjoerds, Z., Teperek, M., Van Den Akker, O. R., Van't Veer, A., & Zurita-Milla, R. (2021). Towards wide-scale adoption of open science practices: The role of open science communities. *Science and Public Policy*, 48(5), 605–611. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scab039>
- Bertram, M. G., Sundin, J., Roche, D. G., Sánchez-Tójar, A., Thoré, E. S. J., & Brodin, T. (2023). Open science. *Current Biology*, 33(15), R792–R797. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2023.05.036>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2019). Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 11(4), 589–597. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1628806>
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2022). *Thematic Analysis: A Practical Guide*. SAGE. <https://www.thematicanalysis.net/>
- Burr, V. (2015). *Social constructionism* (Third edition). Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- Burton, S. (2021). Solidarity, now! Care, Collegiality, and Comprehending the Power Relations of 'Academic Kindness' in the Neoliberal Academy. *Performance Paradigm*, 16, 20–39. <https://openaccess.city.ac.uk/id/eprint/26939/>
- Cole, N. L., Kormann, E., Klebel, T., Apartis, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). The societal impact of Open Science: A scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 11(6), 240286. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240286>
- Disciplines covered by the endorsing bodies for science, engineering, humanities, social science and medicine*. (n.d.). GOV.UK. Retrieved 12 August 2024, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/global-talent-endorsing-bodies/disciplines-covered-by-the-endorsing-bodies-for-science-engineering-humanities-and-medicine>
- Dusdal, J., & Powell, J. J. W. (2021). Benefits, Motivations, and Challenges of International Collaborative Research: A Sociology of Science Case Study. *Science and Public Policy*, 48(2), 235–245. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scab010>
- Fecher, B., & Friesike, S. (2014). Open Science: One Term, Five Schools of Thought. In S. Bartling & S. Friesike (Eds.), *Opening Science* (pp. 17–47). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-00026-8_2

- Fiorini, S., Tezcan, A., Ghent University, Belgium, Vanallemeersch, T., CrossLang, Belgium, Szoc, S., CrossLang, Belgium, Migdisi, K., CrossLang, Belgium, Meeus, L., CrossLang, Belgium, Macken, L., & Ghent University, Belgium. (2023). Translations and Open Science Exploring how translation technologies can support multilingualism in scholarly communication. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Human-Informed Translation and Interpreting Technology 2023*, 41–51. https://doi.org/10.26615/issn.2683-0078.2023_004
- Gagliardi, D., Cox, D., & Li, Y. (2015). Institutional Inertia and Barriers to the Adoption of Open Science. In *The Transformation of University Institutional and Organizational Boundaries* (pp. 107–133). Brill. <https://brill.com/display/book/edcoll/9789463001786/BP000007.xml>
- Gownaris, N. J., Vermeir, K., Bittner, M.-I., Gunawardena, L., Kaur-Ghumaan, S., Lepenies, R., Ntsefong, G. N., & Zakari, I. S. (2022). Barriers to Full Participation in the Open Science Life Cycle among Early Career Researchers. *Data Science Journal*, 21, 2. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2022-002>
- Hostler, T. J. (2023). The Invisible Workload of Open Research. *Journal of Trial and Error*, 4(1), 21–36. <https://doi.org/10.36850/mr5>
- Kohrs, F. E., Auer, S., Bannach-Brown, A., Fiedler, S., Haven, T. L., Heise, V., Holman, C., Azevedo, F., Bernard, R., Bleier, A., Bössel, N., Cahill, B. P., Castro, L. J., Ehrenhofer, A., Eichel, K., Frank, M., Frick, C., Friese, M., Gärtner, A., ... Weissgerber, T. L. (2023). Eleven strategies for making reproducible research and open science training the norm at research institutions. *eLife*, 12, e89736. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.89736>
- Langlois, M. (2022). *The struggle between values and practices in radical open organizations* [Phdthesis, Université Paris sciences et lettres]. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-04055090>
- Leonelli, S. (2022). Open Science and Epistemic Diversity: Friends or Foes? *Philosophy of Science*, 89(5), 991–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1017/psa.2022.45>
- Leonelli, S. (2023). *Philosophy of Open Science* (1st ed.). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009416368>
- Making Open Science a Reality* (OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers 25; OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, Vol. 25). (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>
- Mozilla Open Leaders*. (n.d.). Mozilla Foundation. Retrieved 15 March 2025, from <https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/initiatives/mozilla-open-leaders/>
- OLS (Director). (2021, February 22). *OLS-3 Week 2 Cohort call 1: Welcome to Open Life Science!* [Video recording]. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IFaMk01Z_gY
- OLS-3-Talks*. (n.d.). YouTube. Retrieved 18 January 2025, from <http://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL1CvC6Ez54KDvJbbdLn5rPvf1kInifEh9>
- Open Science | OLS*. (n.d.). Retrieved 18 January 2025, from <https://we-are-ols.org/open-science.html>
- Persic, A., Beigel, F., Hodson, S., & Oti-Boateng, P. (2021). The time for open science is now. In *UNESCO Science Report: The race against time for smarter development*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.
- Pownall, M., Azevedo, F., König, L. M., Slack, H. R., Evans, T. R., Flack, Z., Grinschgl, S., Elsherif, M. M., Gilligan-Lee, K. A., De Oliveira, C. M. F., Gjoneska, B., Kalandadze, T., Button, K., Ashcroft-Jones, S., Terry, J., Albayrak-Aydemir, N., Dëchtërenko, F., Alzahawi, S., Baker, B. J., ... FORRT. (2023). Teaching open and reproducible scholarship: A critical review of the evidence base for current pedagogical methods and their outcomes. *Royal Society Open Science*, 10(5), 221255. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.221255>
- Ramírez-Castañeda, V. (2020). Disadvantages in preparing and publishing scientific papers caused by the dominance of the English language in science: The case of Colombian researchers in biological sciences. *PLOS ONE*, 15(9), e0238372. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0238372>

- Roberts, L. E. (2020). *Opening Academia: An Activity Theory Analysis of How Academics Learn and Do Openness*. <https://www.lib.ncsu.edu/resolver/1840.20/38182>
- Thibault, R. T., Amaral, O. B., Argolo, F., Bandrowski, A. E., Davidson, A. R., & Drude, N. I. (2023). Open Science 2.0: Towards a truly collaborative research ecosystem. *PLOS Biology*, *21*(10), e3002362. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002362>
- UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>
- Ursić, L., Bralić, N., Žuljević, M. F., Puljak, L., & Buljan, I. (2024). Exploring the understanding of reproducibility among stakeholders within academia and their expectations for a web-based education tool: A qualitative study. *Accountability in Research*, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2345723>
- Welcome to OLS stats—OLS Stats*. (n.d.). Retrieved 18 January 2025, from <https://we-are-ols.org/ols-stats/>
- Williams, J. J., Tractenberg, R. E., Batut, B., Becker, E. A., Brown, A. M., Burke, M. L., Busby, B., Cooch, N. K., Dillman, A. A., Donovan, S. S., Doyle, M. A., Van Gelder, C. W. G., Hall, C. R., Hertweck, K. L., Jordan, K. L., Jungck, J. R., Latour, A. R., Lindvall, J. M., Lloret-Llinares, M., ... Woodley, L. (2023). An international consensus on effective, inclusive, and career-spanning short-format training in the life sciences and beyond. *PLOS ONE*, *18*(11), e0293879. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0293879>